

NOTES

Alpha-Picoline Complexes of Cyanide, Thiocyanate and Cyanate of Copper. Silver and Mercury Part, II-Dissociation Pressures and Pressure-Composition isothermals of Cyanide Thiocyanate and Cyanate of Copper

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A systematic study of the complexes of α -picoline with metal salts was made by Bhattacharya and Sinha². They have prepared and studied the complexes of sulphates and thiocyanates of zinc, cadmium, nickel and cobalt.

In the present work we have studied α -picoline complexes of the cyanide, thiocyanate and cyanate of copper. Two series of measurements were carried out with each complex. One was to study the dissociation pressures at fixed temperatures for varying compositions of picoline complex, with a view to identifying the different kinds of stable complexes formed, each differing from the other in its picoline content. The other was to study the dissociation pressures of these complexes at varying temperatures so as to obtain the thermodynamic heat of formation leading to the evaluation of the stability of the complex.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation, analysis and properties of these complexes have been given in our previous paper³.

Pressure-composition Isothermal; The apparatus used was essentially the same as that used by Bhattacharya and Sinha². The method consisted mainly in the measurements of the loss in the weight of picoline with its gradual removal at a fixed temperature with a simultaneous measurement of pressure. The loss of weight of the bulb containing the complex with progressive removal of α -picoline was determined by weighing the bulb at several intervals and the corresponding dissociation pressures were measured with the help of mercury manometer. Thus a series of pressure values and the corresponding weights were obtained. The compound in the bulb was analysed after the experiment and ratio of picoline to metal was calculated. The isothermals were drawn at 50° in case of thiocyanate and cyanide complexes and

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1. Sinha and Ray, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1948 44, 790.
2. Bhattacharya and Sinha—*Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 32, 317, 414.
3. Chauhan and Sinha, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40 769.

at 35° in case of cyanate complex. The results of the pressures were plotted against the number of molecules of α -picoline.

Dissociation Pressure :—The dissociation pressures of the complexes were measured at different temperatures using the same apparatus as described by Ray and Sinha¹ and from the data the heat of dissociation, which gave a measure of the stability of the complex, was calculated. An electrically operated air thermostat, kept constant to $\pm 0.1^\circ$ was used. The thermostat was set at different temperatures and when equilibrium was attained, the pressure was obtained from the difference in the heights of mercury in the manometer.

The range of temperature over which the dissociation pressures were measured were not the same for all compounds, due to the fact that some compounds showed very low dissociation pressures at the lower temperatures whereas some were stable only at the lower temperatures. In some cases the compound which was stable at lower temperature changed over to another crystalline modification at higher temperature.

The logarithms of dissociation pressures plotted against $10^6/T$ was linear. The value of the heat of dissociation for each compound is given in table I.

TABLE I

<i>Mean value of heat of dissociation</i>	
CuCN : 2 Pico — α	19.82 Cals.
" " — β	8.15 Cals.
CuCN : 1 Pico	9.63 Cals.
CuCNS : 2 Pico — α	16.3 Cals.
" " — β	9.196 Cals.
CuCNS : 1 Pico	9.395 Cals.
Cu(CNO) ₂ : 2 Pico	11.5 Cals.
Cu(CNO) ₂ : 1 Pico	11.6 Cals.

DISCUSSION

Graphically it is indicated that at 50° there are two distinct and definite solid phases in the cases of α -picoline complexes of CuCN and CuCNS. These solid phases correspond to the stoichiometric compositions CuCN : 1 Pico, CuCN : 5 Pico, CuCNS : 1 Pico and CuCNS ; 2 Pico. The phases corresponding to Cu (CNO)₂ : 2Pico seems to decompose at temperatures above 50°. It is, however, present at 35°. The phase corresponding to Cu(CNO)₂ : 1 Pico, however exists at both the temperatures.

From a study of dissociation pressures at varying temperatures and a graph of $\log_{10}P$ vs $10^6/T$, evidence for the existence of the same compound in two crystalline forms is obtained. Thus CuCN : 2Pico and CuCNS ; 2Pico are found to exist in two

distinct crystalline forms, changing over from one form to the other at certain fixed temperatures. These transition temperatures are mentioned in table II.

TABLE II

Compound	Crystalline Form		Transition Temperature
	Higher Temp.	Lower Temp.	
CuCN : 2Pico	monoclinic or triclinic	orthorhombic	$53.5 \pm 1^\circ$
CuCNS : 2Pico	orthorhombic	monoclinic or triclinic	$43.2 \pm 1^\circ$

Usually the heat of dissociation of a complex containing a higher number of ligands is less than that of one having a lower number. But in the case of the varieties of the cyanide and thiocyanate complexes, the values of the heat of dissociation for the lower picolinated complexes are less than those of the higher picolinated one. Such anomalous behaviour has been noticed by some other workers also.

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